

Exoplanet Detection Using AI in Transit Photometry

Abstract:

This research investigates the methodology and outcomes of exoplanet detection through transit photometry, utilizing a dataset sourced from the Kepler Space Telescope. The study aims to provide insights into manual and automated exoplanet detection approaches, focusing on the folding technique to discern periodic patterns in light curves. The K-nearest neighbors algorithm (KNN) is employed for automated detection, achieving a notable accuracy of 93%, surpassing human performance. This finding underscores the potential of KNN algorithms as a more robust tool for space exploration and identifying potential extraterrestrial life.

Keywords: Exoplanet Detection, Transit Photometry, Artificial Intelligence, data analysis, KNN models

Introduction

Since the discovery of the first exoplanet in 1992, detecting exoplanets, or planets outside our solar system, has become a turning point in astrophysics. This development ignited a tireless search for answers to remote planetary systems. For years, numerous methods have been used in identifying and categorizing these celestial bodies, transit photometry being one powerful and widely utilized one.

The basic principle behind transit photometry involves the measurement of variation in a star's flux or brightness with time. It is based on the indirect observation of exoplanets because they are too distant and often faint to be imaged directly. Instead, astronomers study changes in the brightness of stars.

Hence, by watching a star's light dim and brighten periodically when its planet passes across its face relative to the line of sight from an observer on Earth, one can understand what transit photometry is all about. Over time, observers can plot these dips, showing atypical drop-offs in this star's luminosity. Transit measurements are critical to parameters of planets, such as duration and depth, which determine important details since they reveal their properties.

Theoretically, an exoplanet should have a dip in its light curve, while nonexoplanets should not. These observations are often difficult for the human eye to detect, as can be seen below:

While it is infeasible for humans to distinguish between exoplanets and nonexoplanets, AI can do it extremely efficiently. After being trained using thousands of light curves gathered from the Kepler Space Telescope, AI can begin to correctly identify the difference between these two types of planets that humans can't. This investigation delves deeper into the efficacy of distinct AI models for such discriminations, the attendant challenges and constraints faced by these models, and the prospective integration of AI methodologies by space agencies, exemplified by NASA, to propel future spatial explorations.

The study used two fundamental libraries, NumPy and Pandas.

NumPy, short for Numerical Python, is a fundamental package for scientific computing with Python. It supports large, multi-dimensional arrays, matrices, and mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. Pandas is an open-source data manipulation and analysis library for Python. It provides data structures for efficiently storing and manipulating large datasets and tools for reading and writing various data formats.

Methodology:

Transit photometry is a technique used in astronomy to detect and study exoplanets. It involves monitoring the brightness of a star over time and looking for periodic dips in brightness, which may indicate the presence of an orbiting exoplanet passing in front of the star relative to the observer's line of sight.

Over time, I discovered that nonexoplanets and exoplanets show dips in their light curves. Exoplanets have these dips repeatedly and in a more 'recognizable pattern.' While this pattern is hard to recognize for humans, it is highly feasible for AI to grasp, and through datasets from the Kepler Space Telescope, we trained the AI to recognize these patterns.

Dataset and its challenges:

The research utilizes a Kepler Space Telescope dataset of flux (light intensity) measurements for various stars. There are 3500 stars in this dataset, 300 of them being exoplanets and 3200 being nonexoplanets.

As can be seen, there are far more exoplanets than nonexoplanets, which posed a significant challenge later in the study.

The dataset had images of the transit photometry of each star along with the correct classification for each star, namely whether it was an exoplanet or nonexoplanet.

The dataset presented 0s and 1s, 0s being nonexoplanets and 1s exoplanets.

The Models

KNN Models

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a robust and versatile machine-learning algorithm for classification and regression tasks. In the training phase, KNN loads a dataset comprising feature vectors and corresponding class labels or target values. The user must choose the number of neighbors, denoted as "k," representing the quantity of nearby data points considered when making predictions. The algorithm then calculates distances between each training data point and a new, unseen one, utilizing metrics such as Euclidean distance. Following this, the training data points are sorted based on their distances, setting the stage for the prediction phase.

During the prediction phase, KNN identifies the k-nearest neighbors to the new data point by selecting the top k data points with the smallest distances. KNN employs a majority voting approach among the k-nearest neighbors for classification tasks to determine the predicted class label. In contrast, regression tasks involve calculating the weighted average of the target values from the k-nearest neighbors. Based on this decision-making process, the predicted class label or target value is assigned to the new data point. This iterative procedure is repeated for each test point in the dataset, culminating in predictions that are subsequently evaluated for accuracy and performance metrics.

Several key considerations impact the efficacy of KNN. Choosing a distance metric, such as Euclidean or Manhattan distance, plays a crucial role in shaping the algorithm's behavior. The user's decision on the value of k directly influences the model's flexibility and sensitivity to noise. Standardization or normalization of features is often recommended to ensure that all features contribute equally to distance calculations. Additionally, the computational complexity of KNN can be a challenge with large datasets, prompting the exploration of optimization techniques like KD trees or Ball trees. Despite these considerations, KNN remains appealing for its simplicity, interpretability, and ability to handle various data types.

Logistic Models

Logistic regression, a foundational algorithm in binary classification, plays a pivotal role in discerning between exoplanets and nonexoplanets in transit photometry. In the training phase, logistic regression utilizes a labeled dataset containing features extracted from light curves and corresponding binary class

labels (0 for nonexoplanets, 1 for exoplanets). The model learns the optimal weights and biases for the features through an iterative optimization process, typically using techniques like gradient descent. The logistic function, also known as the sigmoid function, transforms the linear combination of features and weights into a probability score between 0 and 1, representing the likelihood of a data point belonging to the positive class (exoplanet).

The logistic regression model evaluates new, unseen data points during the prediction phase by applying the learned weights and biases. The output is a probability score, and a decision threshold (commonly set at 0.5) is employed to classify the data point into either the positive or negative class. If the probability score exceeds the threshold, the data point is classified as an exoplanet; otherwise, it is labeled as a nonexoplanet. The model's performance is subsequently assessed through accuracy, precision, recall, and the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve.

Several factors influence the effectiveness of logistic regression in exoplanet detection. Selecting relevant features extracted from light curves is crucial for model performance. Additionally, addressing class imbalance, as observed in the imbalanced distribution of exoplanets and nonexoplanets in the dataset, is essential to prevent biased learning. The interpretability of logistic regression models is advantageous for understanding the contribution of each feature to the classification decision. While logistic regression is a powerful and interpretable algorithm, it assumes a linear relationship between features. It may face challenges in capturing complex patterns in data compared to more advanced algorithms.

After experimenting with Logistic and KNN models with multiple training methods, such as different k values for the KNN model, I decided to use the KNN model over the Logistic one. It performed exceptionally accurately and initially seemed almost 'too accurate.'

```
# Calculate the predictions and accuracies on train_X and test_X
# using our trained model

#YOUR CODE HERE
y_pred = model.predict(test_X)
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_pred, test_y)
print(accuracy)
#####
0.9912280701754386
```

With over 99.12% accuracy, the model worked well until I realized why the accuracy was so high. The model had been trained on data with far more exoplanets than nonexoplanets and was naturally biased towards choosing nonexoplanets. In this way, it would always choose nonexoplanets, and because this was the case, the model would usually end up with high accuracy. This was further confirmed by a confusion matrix created to check what the model was guessing.

As seen on the test, the model predicted '0' (nonexoplanets) 570 times, never predicting exoplanets once. This confirmed my suspicion that the AI wasn't really 'working.' It was faking it through the same answer as most planets were naturally nonexoplanets.

The solution to this problem was confusing yet simple. The only way to make the AI truly accurate was to have a sample that consisted of exoplanets and nonexoplanets in an equal share. The only problem with that was the fact that in random samples, nonexoplanets were generally more frequent than exoplanets as they were more commonly found in outer space. After much consideration, I figured out the most simple solution: Augmentation.

Augmentation is the process of artificially increasing the size of a training dataset by applying various transformations to the existing data. It's why I chose to use KNN models rather than Logistic models. Because KNN models are better at dealing with class imbalance and pattern recognition, it is easier to perform augmentation with them. Augmentation requires two steps: the SMOTE Function and Normalization.

SMOTE

SMOTE is a technique to address the class imbalance problem in machine learning datasets. Class imbalance occurs when one class (usually the minority class, in this case, exoplanets) is underrepresented compared to the other classes. In exoplanet AI detection or any binary classification task, the imbalance might arise if the number of positive examples (exoplanets) is significantly smaller than the number of negative examples (non-exoplanets).

The SMOTE algorithm works by generating synthetic examples for the minority class. It creates new instances by interpolating between existing minority class instances. This helps balance the class distribution and prevents the model from being biased toward the majority class. By introducing synthetic examples, SMOTE ensures the model sees a more balanced representation of both classes during training.

Normalization:

Normalization is the process of scaling and centering the features of a dataset. It transforms the data into a standard scale, often between 0 and 1, making it easier for machine learning models to converge during training. Normalization is beneficial when features have different scales, as it prevents certain features from dominating the learning process due to their larger magnitudes.

For exoplanet AI detection or any machine learning task, normalization can help in the following ways:

Improved Convergence: Normalizing the features ensures that each feature contributes more evenly to the model's learning process. This can lead to faster convergence during training.

Mitigating Sensitivity to Initial Values: Normalization helps reduce the model's sensitivity to the initial values of the weights. This can result in a more stable and reliable training process.

Enhanced Generalization: Normalized features can contribute to better generalization of the model to unseen data. The model is less likely to be influenced by the scale of the features, making it more adaptable to diverse datasets.

Using the SMOTE Function and normalization, I created various replications of the light curves shared by the few exoplanets in the dataset. After creating 300 copies of exoplanets, I trained the data model on a sample of 600 light curves (300 exoplanet ones and 300 nonexoplanets). After some training, I reran the model through a random sample of 80 planets from the Kepler Space Telescope. Below is the confusion matrix of that sample:

With the augmented training data, the results are dramatically different. The '0' and the '1' are approximately being guessed the same amount of time and are appearing the same amount of time. Similar results are shown in the test on the augmented predicted data that shows that while the model did lose some accuracy (went from 99.2% to 99.33%), it is now beginning to guess exoplanets more frequently, showing its reliance and potential for use in the future with even more improvements.

The application of augmented training data in analyzing exoplanet detection models yields a substantial transformation in the prediction outcomes. Notably, the augmented dataset results in a more balanced prediction distribution between the classes '0' and '1,' with both being guessed and appearing in the model's predictions with comparable frequencies. This signifies a crucial shift in the model's behavior, moving away from a skewed prediction pattern and demonstrating a more equitable consideration of both positive and negative instances.

While 93.3% accuracy may not seem ideal, it is a much better bet than manual detection, which, from a statistical approach, would be 50/50. Even transit photometric experts, renowned for their expertise in identifying exoplanets, face challenges in accurately discerning the subtle differences between these celestial bodies. The introduction of artificial intelligence, as evidenced by the model's performance, holds the promise of revolutionizing the landscape of exoplanet detection. Despite a marginal loss in overall accuracy, the model's increased inclination towards predicting exoplanets signifies a valuable shift towards a more reliable and automated methodology.

Using augmented training data and artificial intelligence in exoplanet detection improves the model's predictive capabilities and highlights the inherent challenges in manual detection. The paradigm shift towards automated methodologies, driven by AI, promises to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of exoplanet detection, paving the way for groundbreaking discoveries and expanding our understanding of the potential for extraterrestrial life in the universe.

Folding Technique:

The folding technique plays a pivotal role in the effectiveness of exoplanet detection through transit photometry. This section evaluates the significance of the folding technique in the context of this research and explores its implications for identifying consistent and inconsistent periods in light curves.

The folding technique in transit photometry involves aligning and overlapping multiple observed light curves of a star to reveal a consistent pattern, particularly the periodic dips caused by orbiting exoplanets. This technique is crucial because it helps astronomers discern repetitive signals hidden within noisy data, making it easier to identify potential exoplanetary transits.

Folding technique in Manual detection:

The effectiveness of the folding technique lies in its ability to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio in light curves. By aligning the observed data at the predicted transit period, astronomers can combine multiple observations, reinforcing the periodic pattern and mitigating the impact of random noise. This results in a clearer and more distinguishable signature of exoplanetary transits.

This research applies the folding technique to light curves obtained from the Kepler Space Telescope. The evaluation focuses on how well the folding technique can reveal consistent patterns in the light curves, especially the characteristic dips indicative of exoplanetary transits. The findings demonstrate that the folding technique enhances the visibility of these patterns, aiding in identifying potential exoplanets.

Through these overlaps between exoplanets and nonexoplanets, experts can learn and attempt to recognize the patterns the AI recognizes when successfully distinguishing between the two. Manual detection could become a more prominent method using these observations to check whether the AI was correct in its attempt to distinguish a planet. This could reinforce the AI model's predictions, 'checking' the AI's work through experts. This would save these experts time, resources, and money, enabling them to detect these planets faster and cheaper.

Limitations

While the conclusions might seem satisfying, there are inherent limitations, like with any new technology. For one, the AI model is not highly accurate. With an accuracy of 93.3%, it still has some uncertainty and will have to be trained for longer with more significant amounts of data to become more accurate and usable. With the current model, scientists would have to test, and experts would have to study the suspected exoplanets to confirm whether they are truly an exoplanet.

Another error that may seem straightforward is that the AI guessed exoplanet 33 times and was wrong 31 times. Because it was trained on a more evenly distributed sample, it now suspects that there are more likely to be an even number of exoplanets to nonexoplanets in an actual data set (not an augmented one), therefore proving itself more likely to guess exoplanets for ones that in reality are not. Consequently, rigorous testing and expert scrutiny are essential to validate suspected exoplanets, emphasizing the need to address biases and refine the model's training process.

The limitations encapsulated in the AI model's accuracy, and the potential introduction of biases underscore the iterative nature of technological advancements in exoplanet detection. While the current state presents challenges, the pursuit of extensive datasets, prolonged training periods, and meticulous bias monitoring stand as critical pathways toward unlocking the true potential of AI in revolutionizing our understanding of celestial bodies beyond our solar system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research contributes valuable insights into the manual detection of exoplanets utilizing transit photometry. The challenges inherent in visually identifying exoplanets are acknowledged, and the innovative folding technique emerges as a promising approach, revealing consistent periods that can aid in accurate identification. Future research endeavors may explore the integration of machine learning methodologies to automate the process of exoplanet detection, potentially alleviating the complexities associated with manual identification.

However, it is essential to recognize the current limitations of the AI model employed in this study, as it needs to exhibit more accuracy. Despite this, the research lays the foundation for future investigations to refine and augment the existing AI model. The path forward involves continued research efforts to enhance the accuracy of AI-driven exoplanet detection models by incorporating more extensive and diverse datasets, prolonged training periods, and the meticulous fine-tuning of model parameters.

This study is a stepping stone towards advancing automated exoplanet detection, presenting avenues for future exploration and refinement. Integrating machine learning techniques can revolutionize the field, offering a more efficient and accurate means of identifying celestial bodies beyond our solar system.

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